

1 **Interactive effects of temperature and precipitation on soil respiration in a**
2 **temperate maritime pine forest.**

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19 **Running head: temperature and rain effects on soil respiration**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Soil respiration (SR) was monitored periodically throughout 2001 in a Scots pine (*Pinus*
3 *sylvestris* L.) stand located in the Belgian Campine region. As expected for a temperate
4 maritime forest, temperature dominated control over SR during most of the year.

5 However, during late spring and summer, when soil water content (SWC) was limiting,
6 SR was insensitive to temperature ($Q_{10}= 1.24$). We observed that during prolonged rain-
7 free periods, when SWC was below 15 vol. %, SR decreased dramatically (up to 50%)
8 and SWC took over control of SR. During such drought-stressed periods, however, rain
9 events sometimes stimulated SR and restored temperature control over SR, even though
10 SWC in the mineral soil indicated severe drought stress. We hypothesize that restoration
11 of the temperature control only occurred when rain events adequately rewetted the
12 uppermost soil layers, where most of the respiratory activity is located. To quantify the
13 rewetting capacity of rain events, an index (I_w) was designed that incorporated rainfall
14 intensity, time elapsed since the last rain event, and atmospheric vapor pressure deficit (a
15 proxy for evaporative water losses). To simulate SR fluxes, a model was developed that
16 included effects of soil temperature, and, under drought and non-rewetting conditions (I_w
17 and $SWC < \text{threshold}$), also a SWC response function. The model explained 95% of the
18 temporal variability in SR observed during summer, whereas the temperature function
19 alone explained only 73% of this variability. Our results reveal that, in addition to
20 temperature and SWC, also rain plays a role in determining the total amount of carbon
21 released from soils, even in a maritime climate.

22

23 *Keywords:* Q_{10} , soil temperature, soil water content, precipitation, drought stress, Scots
24 *pine.*

25

1 **Introduction**

2 Soil respiration (SR) is an important component of forest ecosystem carbon (C) budgets.
3 Forest soils contain large C stores (Post et al., 1982) and it has been hypothesized that
4 relatively small climate change-induced changes in soil respiration could rival the annual
5 fossil fuel loading of atmospheric CO₂ (Jenkinson et al. 1992, Raich and Schlesinger
6 1992). On a global scale, SR is mainly controlled by temperature and precipitation (Raich
7 & Schlesinger 1992, Raich et al. 2002). Since global temperatures and precipitation
8 patterns are expected to change in the future (Borken et al. 1999), this may potentially
9 alter CO₂ fluxes from soils (Raich et al. 2002). Thus, it is very relevant to understand
10 which are the climatic factors that control soil respiration and, moreover, how these
11 factors affect the emissions of CO₂ from soils. Where no severe drought stress occurs,
12 soil temperature typically is a reliable predictor of soil respiration (Moncrieff and Fang
13 1999). However, other biotic and abiotic factors have been reported to influence soil
14 respiration: soil water content (Carlyle & Than 1988, Howard & Howard 1993, Keith et
15 al. 1997, Epron et al. 1999, Law et al. 1999; Reichstein et al 2002), soil organic matter
16 quantity and quality (Taylor et al., 1989), root and microbial biomass, root nitrogen
17 content (Ryan et al. 1996), soil acidity, soil texture and site productivity (Raich and
18 Schlesinger 1992, Raich and Potter 1995). Under drought conditions, also the amount and
19 distribution of precipitation has been indicated as an important controlling factor of SR
20 (Borken et al. 1999, Lee et al. 2002, Rey et al. 2002). Rain exerts its control during dry
21 periods either by controlling SWC fluctuations in surface layers where most of the
22 biological activity occurs (Lee et al. 2002) or by strongly stimulating soil CO₂ emissions
23 in what is called the "Birch effect" or "drying and rewetting effect" (Birch 1958, 1960,
24 Andersson 1973, Orchard and Cook 1983, Russell et al. 1998, Borken et al. 1999,
25 Davidson et al. 2000, Lee et al. 2002, Rey et al. 2002). Especially arid and semiarid
26 regions may be more sensitive to changes in precipitation patterns (Rey et al. 2002), but
27 also temperate ecosystems, where precipitation is evenly distributed over the year, may
28 be sensitive to the amount and distribution of rainfall during drought episodes (Borken et
29 al. 1999, Longdoz et al. 2000, Lee et al. 2002).
30 Soil CO₂ efflux has been modeled using linear (Witkamp 1996, Andersson 1973), power
31 (Kucera and Kirkham 1971), and sigmoid (Schlentner and van Cleve 1985, Janssens et al.

1 2000b, Matteucci et al. 2000) relationships with temperature. However, exponential
2 relationships, especially the Q_{10} relationship (van't Hoff 1898), are more frequently used
3 to predict respiration rates from temperature ((Peterjohn et al. 1994, Raich and Potter
4 1995, Boone et al. 1998, Davidson et al. 1998, Epron et al. 1999, Buchmann 2000, Morén
5 and Lindroth 2000). Although there is no agreement on the best shape of the relationship
6 (Lloyd and Taylor 1994), and it has been a matter of controversy whether a function
7 developed to explain temperature effects at a molecular level could be extrapolated to
8 larger scales such as organisms or ecosystems (Chaui-Berlinck et al. 2002), Q_{10} functions
9 often do well at predicting the temporal variation of soil respiration. Most empirical
10 models have used a constant Q_{10} (“annual Q_{10} ”) to predict ecosystem respiratory
11 responses to temperature. However, several authors have pointed out that Q_{10} is not
12 constant during the year, but decreases as temperature increases (Paembonan et al. 1991,
13 Rayment and Jarvis 2000, Tjoelker et al. 2001, Xu and Qi 2001b, Janssens and Pillegard
14 2002). Thus, at synoptic timescales, models with constant parameters may be less
15 accurate than models with seasonally fluctuating parameters. The aims of this study were
16 I. to analyze which climatic factors control SR in different periods of the year and to
17 determine the relationships between the controlling factors and SR. II. To analyze the
18 seasonal changes in the temperature-sensitivity of SR and evaluate which factors may
19 explain these seasonal changes.

20

21 **Materials and Methods**

22

23 *Plot description*

24 This study was conducted in a 72-year old Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) stand, located
25 in Brasschaat, 20 km NE of Antwerpen in the Belgian Campine region (51°18' N and 4°
26 31' E). The stand is part of a larger forest ‘De Inslag’, and is a level-II observation plot of
27 the European Programme for Intensive Monitoring of Forest Ecosystems (EC regulation
28 No. 3528/86 and UN/ECE), managed by the Institute for Forestry and Game
29 Management (Flanders, Belgium). ‘De Inslag’ is also part of the Carboeuroflux research
30 network (<http://www.bgc-jena.mpg.de/public/carboeur/>), funded by the European
31 Commission’s Fifth Framework Programme. Topography at the site is almost flat (slope:

1 0.3%), and the elevation is 16 m. At the time of study (2001), tree density was 376 trees
2 ha⁻¹, with a mean tree height of 21 m and a mean diameter at breast height of 0.29 m
3 (Xiao et al., accepted). In the area where the SR measurements reported here were
4 collected, understorey vegetation was limited to a moss layer (Janssens et al., 1999).
5 The site has a temperate maritime climate, with mean annual temperature of 9.8 °C, and
6 3° C and 18° C as mean temperatures of the coldest and warmest months, respectively
7 (Janssens et al. 1999). Long-term (30 year) mean annual precipitation is 750 mm, and
8 long-term mean annual potential evapotranspiration is 670 mm (Cermák et al. 1998).
9 During the growing season (March to October), total precipitation averages around 433
10 mm, while potential evapotranspiration rates are much higher: 619 mm (Cermák et al.
11 1998), suggesting that drought stress may occur in summer. The forest has a moderately
12 wet, sandy soil (80-98% sand in upper m; Janssens et al., 1999) with a distinct humus
13 and/or iron B-horizon (Baeyens et al., 1993). The soil type is a psammentic haplumbrept
14 (U.S.D.A. classification) or an umbric regosol (F.A.O. classification). Above a depth of 1
15 m, the mineral soil contains 115 t C ha⁻¹, and the surface litter layer contains 27 t C ha⁻¹
16 (Janssens et al, 1999).
17 The site has poor drainage due to a clay layer at a depth of 1.5 to 2 m. The soil is therefor
18 moist, but nonetheless rarely saturated, due to the high hydraulic conductivity in the
19 upper layers (sand). Soil water content (SWC) is typically above water holding capacity
20 (WHC, 0.123 m³ m⁻³), except during summer when SWC frequently drops below WHC
21 (Figure 1). More detailed information on the soil and local climatic conditions can be
22 found in Baeyens et al. (1993), Janssens et al. (1999) and Kowalski et al. (2000).

23

24 *Soil respiration measurements*

25 A closed dynamic system (IRGA: CIRAS-1, soil chamber: SRC-1, both PP-Systems,
26 Hitchin, UK) was used to measure soil respiration. To mitigate spatial variability, we
27 enlarged the surface area sampled by the chamber by attaching a PVC-rim to the base of
28 the chamber. The bottom side of the PVC rim had a slot in which a rubber joint provided
29 an airtight seal for the soil collars (Janssens et al. 2000a). Modification of the chamber
30 did not alter the measured fluxes (Janssens et al. 2000a).

1 Ten PVC-collars (20-cm diameter, 16 cm height) were installed randomly within the
2 experimental plot during November 2000. The lowest 6 cm of each collar were perforated
3 with 5-mm holes to allow fine roots to re-colonize the space within the collar, thus trying
4 to imitate as much as possible the natural conditions. Collars were inserted in the soil,
5 leaving 4 cm exposed. We are aware that fluxes may be modified due to several effects
6 related to the use of collars in this study: the PVC surface, exposed over the soil surface
7 may increase water condensation and therefore within-collar SWC as well as it may
8 artificially protect collar interior against radiation and turbulences. However we believe
9 these effects were minimized because collar was protruded only 4 cm above the ground.
10 The sparse ground vegetation (mosses) was removed very carefully from within the
11 collars just after installation to avoid any bias created by their respiratory activity. The
12 meteorological parameters used in this study were logged continuously in the vicinity of
13 a meteorological tower, 50 m from the experimental plot. Precipitation (tipping-bucket
14 rain gauge, Didcot DRG-51, UK) and air relative humidity (psychrometer, Didcot DTS-
15 5A, UK) measurements were collected at the top of the tower (40 mts), while air
16 temperature was measured at 1.5 m above the forest floor and soil temperature at 2 and 9
17 cm in the mineral soil. Precipitation, relative humidity and air and soil temperature were
18 continuously measured and stored as half-hourly means or totals on a data logger
19 (Campbell CR10, CSI, Logan, UT, USA). Soil water content was measured at two
20 different locations, one with a shallow clay layer (1 m) and one with a deeper clay layer
21 (2 m), at 25 and 30 cm in the mineral soil, respectively, using two 50 cm-long,
22 horizontally-installed TDR probes (Meiressonne & Overloop, 1999). We averaged SWC
23 from both locations because the depth of the clay layer was extremely variable
24 (Meiressonne and Overloop 1999). Measurements were taken about twice a week (cable
25 tester Tectronix 1502B, USA) and were linearly interpolated.
26 Measurements of SR were made frequently during one year from early January 2001 (2
27 months after collars were inserted) until the end of December 2001 (Figure 1a). Each
28 measurement was duplicated and the mean was used in the calculations. No significant
29 differences were found between consecutive measurements (data not shown). SR was
30 pooled over all 10 collars. The dataset was then subdivided in 3 subsets, each

1 representing a different period of the year (winter/early spring, late spring/summer and
2 fall; Figure 1a and Table 1).

3 4 *Temperature responses*

5
6 The temperature response of SR was estimated by means of a Q₁₀ function:

$$7 \quad SR = SR_{10} * Q_{10}^{((T-10)/10)}, \quad \text{equation 1}$$

9
10 in which SR is the predicted soil respiration, SR₁₀ is the simulated SR at 10°C, Q₁₀ is the
11 temperature sensitivity of SR (the respiratory flux at one temperature over the flux at a
12 temperature 10°C lower), and T is the measured soil temperature at 2 cm in the mineral
13 soil. The function was fitted first to the entire annual data set and finally to each of the 3
14 periods to test for seasonal changes in Q₁₀. To avoid confounding effects of drought on
15 the temperature response, the following data were removed from the datasets: I.
16 Measurements taken under drought conditions, defined as SWC below WHC (0.123 m m⁻³) II.
17 Measurements taken more than 30 hours after the last significant rain event (> 1 mm
18 h⁻¹). These data were excluded, because the upper layers, where most of the organic
19 matter and fine roots are located (Janssens et al. 2002b), dry out rapidly. Therefore,
20 drought could occur in these upper layers, even if SWC at 25 cm is above WHC. III.
21 Measurements taken just after a rain event. These data were excluded to avoid possible
22 stimulative effects due to rewetting of the upper soil layers_(Lee et al. 2002, Rey et al.
23 2002, Kelliher et al. 1999, Birch 1958, 1960, Anderson 1973). Thus, SR₁₀ and Q₁₀ were
24 estimated under unlimited moisture conditions and avoiding confounding effects by rain.
25 Only in period 3, corresponding to late spring and summer data were excluded.

26 27 *Drought and rain effects*

28
29 When SWC was below WHC, the following model was fitted to the data:

$$30 \quad SR = f(T) * f(SWC), \quad \text{equation 2}$$

31

1

2 Where SR is the soil respiration, $f(T)$ a Q_{10} function and $f(SWC)$ a linear function
3 depending on SWC:

4

$$5 \quad f(SWC) = a * SWC + b, \quad \text{equation 3}$$

6

7 Where SWC is soil water content in $m^3 m^{-3}$, and a and b are parameters (5.2 and -0.05
8 respectively).

9

10 However, very often we observed that, under limited SWC conditions, SR was enhanced
11 by significant rain events in such a degree that temperature control over SR was restored.
12 Hence, application of *equation 3* was restricted to those measurements where no
13 rewetting occurred. To define where rewetting was significant and where not, we needed
14 to quantify the rewetting potential of rain events. We assumed that rewetting capacity
15 would be positively related to the water inputs (amount of precipitation) and negatively to
16 the water losses (evaporation, uptake by roots and percolation). Because percolation and
17 uptake by roots were impossible to estimate, we used time since the last rain event as a
18 proxy for these water losses. Also evaporation was not measured. Because vapor flux
19 density is positively related with the atmospheric vapor pressure deficit (VPD_a ; Penman-
20 Monteith equation), we used VPD_a as a proxy for the evaporative water losses from the
21 soil surface.

22 Thus, quantification of the rewetting capacity by rain events was simulated with a
23 rewetting index (I_w) that included the absolute amount of precipitation during the rain
24 event, VPD_a , and time since the last rain in *equation 4*. We obtained the best fit with a
25 logarithmic function of the form:

26

$$27 \quad I_w = a + \text{Log} [\text{sqrt} (R) / (VPD_a * (t)^2)], \quad \text{equation 4} \quad (\text{See also Figure 2})$$

28

29 Where a is a constant (2.5), R represents the amount of precipitation during the last
30 rainfall event (mm), t is the time in hours since the last rain event (h) and VPD_a the mean
31 vapor pressure deficit of the atmosphere at 1.5 m above the forest floor (kPa), averaged

1 over the last 24 h. We observed that the effect of rain was relatively independent of its
2 intensity (Figure 2a and 2c). Therefore we minimized its contribution by using the square
3 root of the rain intensity in *equation 4*. Time, in contrast, was very critical because the
4 rain stimulation was highly ephemeral (Figure 2b and 2c). We therefore maximized the
5 contribution of time by using the square of the elapsed time in *equation 4*.

6 Thus, I_w was intended to be a rough representation of the rewetting intensity in the upper
7 soil layers where no moisture sensors were installed. Because we observed that, when I_w
8 was above 0.3, temperature resumed control over the measured fluxes, we applied the
9 SWC correction only when I_w was below 0.3. Figure 2 shows bi-dimensional
10 representations of the relationship among the three variables controlling I_w . Even
11 relatively small rain events ($< 4\text{mm}$) were able to rewet the uppermost layers sufficient to
12 restore temperature control ($I_w > 0.3$, Figures 2a and 2c). I_w decreased rapidly with time,
13 especially during the first hours (Figure 2c). Furthermore, Figure 2a and 2b show that
14 even at the highest values of VPD_a , I_w may be longer than 0.3 for extended time periods
15 when precipitation exceeded 3-4 mm.

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1 **Results and discussion**

3 *Temperature control over SR*

4 Seasonal differences in SR rates were large, with fluxes ranging between 0.3 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
5 in January and 2.3 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in late July (Figure 1a). Temperature was the main
6 controlling factor over SR during most of the year (Table 1, Figure 3). Only during the
7 growing season, temperature control over SR was limited (Table 1, Figure 3), suggesting
8 that other factors may exert a strong influence on SR during this season. When all
9 potentially drought-affected data were excluded, a tight relationship between temperature
10 and SR was observed also in summer (see graph named as “Period 2” in Figure 3).

11 The annual Q_{10} function explained a large proportion of the temporal variation in SR (R^2
12 = 0.68; Table 1). When drought affected data were excluded from the analysis, the annual
13 Q_{10} increased from 1.93 to 2.9 (Table 1), a value well within the range (2.0 – 6.3)
14 reported for European and North-American forest ecosystems (Davidson *et al.*, 1998;
15 Janssens *et al.*, 2001). This increase in Q_{10} , together with the significant improvement of
16 the fit after exclusion of the drought affected data (R^2 from 0.68 to 0.95), emphasizes the
17 confounding effect of drought in the sensitivity of SR to temperature. The annual SR_{10} ,
18 however, was not altered by the exclusion of the drought-affected measurements (Table
19 1). This is because most of our measurements were taken at soil temperatures around 10
20 °C, and none of these measurements at moderate temperatures were drought-affected.
21 Exclusion of a limited number of water-stressed data at higher temperatures therefore had
22 no effect on the mean SR at 10 °C, although it did change the Q_{10} .

23 Seasonal analysis of SR indicated that, even when rain- and drought-affected data were
24 excluded, Q_{10} and SR_{10} varied considerably (Table 1). SR_{10} was maximal during the
25 growing season, but was very similar during winter and fall. This summer increase in
26 basal soil respiration might be related to the typical peak in root growth and biomass that
27 occurs in the growing season (Lyr and Hoffmann 1967). The highest Q_{10} value (3.2)
28 occurred in fall, and the lowest in summer (2.0). In our study, highest Q_{10} didn't coincide
29 with lowest temperature or highest SWC (Table 1). The weak relationship between Q_{10}
30 and SWC was expected, because drought-affected data were removed to avoid
31 confounding effects in the Q_{10} estimates themselves. However, the absence of a

1 relationship between Q_{10} and temperature observed in this study conflicts with strong
2 evidence that the temperature sensitivity of respiration decreases as temperature increases
3 (de Jong and Schappert 1972, Paembonan et al. 1991, Howard and Howard 1993, Lloyd
4 and Taylor 1994, Sprugel et al. 1995, Rayment and Jarvis 2000, Tjoelker et al. 2001, Xu
5 and Qi 2001*b*, Janssens and Pillegard 2002). On the other hand, some of these field
6 studies may have included drought-affected data (Sprugel et al. 1995, Rayment and Jarvis
7 2000, Xu and Qi 2001*b*, Janssens and Pillegard 2002) that may have exacerbated the
8 decrease in Q_{10} at higher temperatures (Xu and Qi 2001*a*). Inclusion of drought affected
9 data in this study decreased Q_{10} in summer significantly from 2.0 to 1.2 (Table 1, Figure
10 3). Because temperature and SWC are often correlated (Davidson et al. 1998), care
11 should therefore be taken when relating changes in Q_{10} to temperature.

12 Another hypothesis that may explain the weak correlation between temperature and Q_{10}
13 may be the temporal scale used in this study. Because of the relatively long periods (3-5
14 months), other factors or processes, *e. g.* seasonality of root growth/mortality or litter
15 inputs during fall, could have confounded the relationship between SR and temperature in
16 some periods, making Q_{10} no longer a measure for the temperature sensitivity only.
17 Different temporal scales have recently been used to study the temperature dependence of
18 SR. Rayment and Jarvis (2000) used a daily time scale basis to calculate Q_{10} , Janssens
19 and Pillegard (2002) choose subsets of typically 4 to 7 days, while Xu and Qi (2001*b*)
20 used approximately one-month periods. However, none of these studies have tried to
21 investigate in depth the relationship between the temporal scale and the resulting Q_{10} of
22 SR. Very short temporal scales would minimize the probability that other factors
23 confound the observed temperature dependence, but are not always realistic because the
24 smaller temperature ranges and the smaller number of flux measurements increase the
25 uncertainty in the calculated Q_{10} values.

26

27 *Drought and rain responses*

28 Even within the maritime climate at our site, SWC became a limiting factor in summer.
29 This was due to the combination of the limited water storage capacity typical to sandy
30 soils (Kelliher et al. 1998) and the relatively long rain-free periods (Figure 1) and high
31 evapotranspiration rates in early summer (Meiresonne et al. 2002). Under conditions of

1 decreasing SWC, it might be expected that the upper soil layers would suffer even more
2 severe drought stress, since evaporation and maximum fine root density (and thus water
3 extraction by roots) occur mainly in these surface layers.

4 After correcting the entire annual data set for temperature, three different subsets of soil
5 fluxes became distinguishable (Figure 4). A first subset of data corresponded to
6 measurements taken with SWC above $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ (Circles in Figure 4). Data included in
7 this subset were obtained mostly outside of summer, with generous and evenly
8 distributed rainfall (Figure 1) and lower evapotranspiration rates (Meiresonne et al,
9 2002). These SR rates were not significantly affected by SWC or post-rainfall effects,
10 and therefore increased exponentially with temperature (fluctuated around 1 after
11 correction for temperature; Figure 4).

12 A second group comprised data obtained under low moisture levels at 25 cm in the
13 mineral soil (SWC below $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$), but with an I_w above the rewetting threshold of
14 0.3 (solid triangles in Figure 4). Similar to the first, unstressed group of measurements,
15 SR rates in this subset were well explained by the Q_{10} function. These measurements
16 were taken just few hours after strong rain events (I_w above the threshold of 0.3)
17 following a period of drought. It is therefore likely that, although the mineral soil was
18 still dry, the surface layers were no longer water-limited. Because most SR originates
19 from these upper layers, temperature control of SR was restored. Only in three
20 measurements, taken less than 5 hours after relatively strong rain events, the rewetting-
21 induced stimulation of SR was not captured well by the model. Davidson et al. (2000)
22 also reported post-rainfall increases in SR under dry conditions, above those expected by
23 a simple matrix potential function. There is an extensive literature discussing these post-
24 rainfall pulses of CO_2 (Birch 1958, 1959, Andersson 1973, Orchard and Cook 1983,
25 Russell et al. 1998, Borken et al. 1999, Davidson et al. 2000, Lee et al. 2002, Rey et al.
26 2002). Stimulation of SR after rainfall has been hypothesized to be due to displacement
27 of CO_2 -rich air from within the soil (Rey et al. 2002), to rapid decomposition of
28 microbial biomass deceased during the drought (Borken et al. 1999) and to an increase in
29 surface area of palatable organic substrates (Birch, 1959) due to desorption of organic
30 molecules from the soil matrix (Serevinatme and Wild, 1985). To date, no consensus has
31 been reached regarding actual causes, duration and magnitude of these post-rainfall

1 stimulative effects. In the maritime climate at this study site, rewetting effects were
2 restricted to measurements taken shortly after rain events during a limited number of
3 drought-stress periods. Hence, there were not enough data to quantitatively assess the
4 relationship between I_w and the magnitude of the post-rainfall effects. However, in
5 general we observed that a sufficiently large I_w restored the temperature control on SR.
6 Therefore, I_w was not directly used in the model, but only to determine if drought reduced
7 SR or not.

8 A third subset (open triangles in Figure 4) comprised data with SWC below $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$
9 and I_w below 0.3. Here, rewetting was absent or marginal, and SR declined linearly with
10 decreasing SWC. The strong control exerted by SWC at 25 cm during periods of scarce
11 rain events and low SWC may suggest that during these periods a major fraction of the
12 fluxes came from deeper layers in the soil profile, and a lesser part from the upper layers.
13 As in most forests, the upper layers of the soil profile at our site are by far the most rich
14 in fine roots and organic matter (Janssens et al. 1999). Most of the respiratory potential is
15 therefore located in these upper layers, which may explain why fluxes dropped
16 dramatically when rain was scarce for prolonged periods and the soil surface started to
17 dry out. Similar results were obtained by Rey et al. (2002), who showed SR to be
18 strongly limited when SWC of the upper 10 cm of soil dropped below a certain threshold.
19 Longdoz et al. (2000) also ascribed an observed summer-decrease in SR to water
20 limitations in the organic layer. Lee et al. (2002) suggested that SWC of the surface
21 layers may be a better predictor of SR rates since “microbial biomass and activity” was
22 likely to be higher in this layers than in deeper ones. Moreover, the amplitude of
23 fluctuations in SWC is larger near the surface (Lee et al. 2002). Therefore, modelling the
24 responses of SR to SWC measured at one depth only may be too simplistic to understand
25 the relationship between SR and SWC (Davidson et al. 2000).

26

27 The model combining the responses of temperature and drought (when SWC was below
28 $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ and I_w was below 0.3), simulated SR rates significantly better than *equation*
29 I alone ($R^2=0.95$, $p<0.0001$ versus $R^2 = 0.72$, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 5). Thus, even in
30 temperate maritime climates, drought can affect total soil C losses significantly during
31 summer periods. The good fit of our model indicates that our approach to quantify the

1 rewetting capacity may be a good and simple solution to model drought responses when
2 no SWC measurements are available in the most active layers.

4 **Conclusions**

5 Soil temperature exerted dominant control over SR during most of the year. Sensitivity of
6 SR to temperature changed significantly during the year. However, we could not find any
7 evidence for control of the temperature sensitivity of SR by temperature or SWC. When
8 SWC decreased below $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, water became the limiting factor and SWC in the
9 mineral soil, as well as the amount and distribution of rainfall exerted a strong influence
10 on SR rates. Our results suggest that, although most of the metabolic activity occurs in
11 the upper centimeters of the soil profile during most of the time, deeper soil layers may
12 become important under severe drought conditions. Therefore, at our site, SR should
13 preferably be modeled using SWC measurements obtained at different depths.

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1 **Figure captions**

2 **Figure 1.** a) Evolution of Soil Respiration under Scots pine overstorey during 2001.
3 Vertical bars represent standard error of the mean. b) Daily mean soil temperature (ST) at
4 2 cm depth in the mineral soil (solid line) and soil water content (SWC) at 25 cm depth in
5 mineral soil (line + square symbol) during 2001. Vertical bars represent standard error of
6 the mean. The horizontal bar represents the water holding capacity ($0.123 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$). c)
7 Time series of daily total precipitation (mm) during 2001. In each graph, vertical bars
8 separate the three different periods assessed in this study (each period numbered in the
9 top of the upper graph).

10 **Figure 2.** Contour graphs illustrating the influence of different parameters on the
11 rewetting index (I_w). a) Effect of Atmospheric Vapor Pressure Deficit (VPD_a , kPa) and
12 amount of precipitation during the last rain event (mm) 10 hours after that rain event. b)
13 Time since the last rain event (hours) and VPD_a (kPa) following 10 mm of precipitation.
14 c) Time since the last rain event (hours) and precipitation during the last rain event (mm)
15 at a VPD_a of 0.75 kPa. The white box indicates the rewetting threshold (0.3).

16 **Figure 3.** Soil respiration as a function of soil temperature at a depth of 2 cm in mineral
17 soil for each of the periods defined in table 1 and its corresponding Q_{10} function (solid
18 line). Dashed line in Period 2 corresponds with Q_{10} fitted to non-drought-affected data
19 only. Solid triangles correspond to drought-affected data and open circles to non-drought-
20 affected measurements. Vertical bars represent standard error of the mean.

21 **Figure 4.** Soil respiration data were normalized for temperature (measured SR was
22 divided by SR predicted from the temperature response under non-water stress
23 conditions) and plotted versus Soil Water Content (SWC) to discriminate the effect of
24 SWC on SR. Fluxes of each period were normalized using their corresponding Q_{10}
25 function. Solid triangles represent data with $\text{SWC} < 0.15$ mm and rewetting Index (I_w) $>$
26 0.3; open triangles represent data with $\text{SWC} < 0.15$ mm and rewetting Index (I_w) $<$ 0.3;
27 solid circles represent data with $\text{SWC} > 0.15$. The solid line represents the linear
28 correction for drought stress.

29 **Figure 5.** Measured versus modeled fluxes for 2001. Solid triangles represent fluxes
30 modeled with both temperature and SWC correction ($f(T)*f(\text{SWC})$ in the figure legend);
31 open circles represent fluxes modeled using the temperature function only ($f(T)$). Fluxes

1 of each period were modeled using their corresponding Q_{10} function. Correlation
2 coefficients (R^2) for each model are also shown. The solid line represents the 1:1 line; the
3 dotted and dashed line represent, respectively, the linear fit for measured fluxes versus
4 fluxes modeled with temperature and SWC and versus fluxes modeled using the
5 temperature function only.
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1 **Table 1** Mean Flux, Q_{10} , soil respiration at 10 °C (SR_{10}), number of observations (n), proportion of variability explained by temperature
 2 (R^2), p-value, Mean Temperature (Mean ST) (°C), and Mean Soil Water Content (Mean SWC) ($m^3 m^{-3}$) for each period. Numbers with
 3 asterisk represent Q_{10} , SR_{10} , R^2 and p-values before excluding the drought affected data. CI is confidence interval as calculated by the
 4 curve-fitting program.

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Period	season	Mean Flux	stdev	Q_{10}	95% CI	SR_{10}	95% CI	n	R^2	p-value	Mean ST	Mean SWC
1-3	Whole year	1.22	0.48	1.93*/2.9	0.12*/0.12	1.06*/1.08	0.04*/0.01	67*/43	0.68*/0.95	<.0001	11.38	0.17
1	winter	0.73	0.20	2.74	0.27	1.02	0.03	18	0.89	<0.0001	6.35	0.24
2	Growing season	1.60	0.32	1.24*/1.98	0.20*/0.4	1.38*/1.23	0.14*/0.1	32*/10	0.06*/0.59	0.184*/0.001	15.45	0.13
3	fall	1.02	0.44	3.21	0.21	1.15	0.03	15	0.96	<0.0001	8.39	0.16

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